

Insights into a Novel CBM from *Bacteroides Caccae* Targeting Tumour-Associated Mucin O-Glycan

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The gastrointestinal tract harbors a diverse community of commensal bacteria that impacts on human health. In a low-fiber diet, some commensal bacteria can switch to host mucin O-glycoproteins as alternative substrates. In this context, the commensal *Bacteroides caccae* was implicated in the deconstruction of the colonic mucous layer, increasing susceptibility to pathogen infection and progression of intestinal diseases^{1,2}. During growth of *B. caccae* on mucin O-glycans, an increase of the expression of modular enzymes, including modular M60-like metallopeptidases (also known as mucinases), with appended non-catalytic carbohydrate-binding modules of family 32 (CBM32), is observed². These enzymes are organized in gene clusters, termed polysaccharide utilization loci (PUL), which encode all the genes necessary for the breakdown and uptake of a given glycan³. Herein, we describe our research advancement using an integrative approach to uncover glycan recognition by a novel CBM32 (BC16100-CBM) appended to a putative mucinase of PUL-53. Analysis using a MUC-1 O-glycopeptide microarray, combined with affinity studies, showed a remarkable specificity towards GalNAc-Ser/GalNAc-Thr (Tn antigen). The molecular determinants of Tn-antigen recognition by BC16100-CBM were elucidated combining NMR and X-ray Crystallography. This data shows the first clues of the molecular mechanism behind the recognition of tumour-associated antigens and utilization of mucin substrates by *B. caccae*.

References

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